

DIFFERENT APPROACHES TO TEACHING ENGLISH AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE TO YOUNG LEARNERS

Qosimova Maxsuda G'anijonovna –

an EFL teacher of school 36, in Fergana, Uzbekistan

Annotation: The article analyzes teaching methods, learning strategies, sense-creative technologies, emotional and psychological peculiarities of teaching English as a foreign language. The purpose of this work is to overcome the challenges facing foreign language learning at a young age in school. The results of the work showed that primary school age can be favorable by imitating abilities of a child, natural curiosity and need for learning a foreign language.

Key words: linguistic intelligence, visual, kinesthetic, interpersonal intelligence, intrapersonal, communicative approach, differentiation method.

Interest in the teaching English to young learners has been steadily growing in recent years. Children who learn a first foreign language at pre-school or primary school levels have a better chance to take a second foreign language in the secondary school from an early age. Children are exposed to the cultures of the countries where the target language is spoken. They grow up tolerant and sympathetic to other people in learning. A foreign language at early age, apart from practical value, stimulates children's ability to use their mother tongue better and learning languages improves children's memory, thinking, perception, imagination, etc. In terms of language skills and fluency, pre-teens and early teens are usually quite alert and confident. They can communicate well in their own language; they are familiar with the basics of such diverse subjects as literature, history and mathematics. They are also beginning to study science as a subject, and to realize that it is a field of knowledge unlike any other. An ideal student, according to any national standards of education, has the ability and the desire to master all those skills, and to use the new information as a tool of self-development on their way to becoming a full-fledged valuable member of society. A great many explanations have been put forward for taking

into account the age, level, and goals of our students. We shall look at young beginners, and the ways to cope with their problems. Young students at the beginner level are naturally curious about all new things. Their minds and memories are uncluttered; they have no fear of the unknown. If they wish to connect with their peers, they may still be able to use non-verbal means of communication. It is interesting, children manage to play together, never feeling any language barriers. Amazingly, they can also retell, translate into their mother tongue what the other children are saying, relay the information to adults, regardless of the language in which it was first received. At a foreign language lesson with young learners, no matter which method we use, we come across the same problem: children tend to rely on the patterns of their native tongue (which they are also still learning to use correctly). On the other hand, once they learn a few words, they are ready to communicate, to talk. Poems and songs are extremely useful, as well as fairy-tales, short plays, cartoons, any and all kinds of visual aids. Have them draw simple diagrams, repeating the same forms over and over again. Children can recite the same poem, listen to the same fairy-tale, sing the same song, and watch the same cartoon hundreds of times. They will enjoy drawing the same picture and laugh at the way grammar can be learned. Psychological and cognitive concepts of EFL learning Teaching techniques and EFL methodological concepts are quite different: from those based on suggestology to cognitive ones. It is impossible to discuss cognitive concepts of language acquisition without reference to Howard Gardner and his noteworthy and influential study of multiple intelligences. Linguistic intelligence is revealed through specially designed grammar and vocabulary exercises based on pair work in dialogues. We can distinguish two stages of working with the language material: first, the teacher presents new materials when the books are closed and then students work on it with their books opened. Visual intelligence is developed when students do exercises supported by pictures or use flash-cards. They reconstruct dialogues and stories with the help of stickers. Musical-rhythmical intelligence is activated when children listen to and imitate intonation and rhythm, sing songs and

rhyme verses. Logical-mathematical intelligence is based on solving problems and puzzles, counting, analyzing elements of the whole, doing “odd one out” tasks. Bodily-kinesthetic intelligence expresses itself in physical activities and movement: role-play, games, making posters and doing projects. Interpersonal intelligence is necessary in pair and group work, games and team activities. Intrapersonal intelligence is based on silent individual work and self-reflection. Only a combination of differently-aimed activities guarantees success in developing pupils' mental abilities together with Communicative skills. In my opinion, English must be similar to learning the first language, where listening goes before speaking. In this way, communicative skills are developed in a natural, spontaneous way. However, some teachers who are used to explaining new structures before teaching pupils to communicate, may add, in small doses, traditional activities such as introducing phonetic transcription, drilling isolated sounds, as well as learning rules. Today, more and more attention is given to communicative approaches in EL teaching. With the emergence of universal education, and the extremely rapid development of ICT, communication became the primary goal for foreign language learners. We live in technological era which has a very important role in education: their use in foreign language teaching raises motivation, facilitates students' cognitive abilities and helps to create a favorable psychological atmosphere in the classroom. This approach gives greater flexibility for language acquisition.

Differentiation method Teaching English to young learners has its own peculiarities based on psychophysiology of their age. Psychologists assert that preschoolers' perception, memory and attention are involuntary. Children cannot regulate their perception and analyze an object. Schoolchildren's attention is drawn by bright objects. Their concentration lasts as long as they are interested in the activity. Therefore, the essential methods of teaching EFL to young learners are based on 3 principles:

1) role plays;

- 2) communicative methods;
- 3) total physical involvement.

Learning a foreign language is a pleasant moment in a child's life. He climbs the stairs to a new level of knowledge. In an effort to teach children the basics of English phonetics, grammar and enrich their vocabulary, a teacher overshadows the individual characteristics of a child, the reaction rate, mental health. Because of this, children cannot move forward in learning knowledge as the basis for successful learning is not only the traditional age principle. Students might be very varied in their prior learning, motivation, learning style, and in other respects. One needs to teach in a way that accommodates these differences, which is called differentiation. The main goal of a differentiation approach is not to provide the necessary minimum in the assimilation of knowledge and skills, but to ensure the greatest possible depth in mastering the material, proper development of abilities of each student. Thus, differentiation involves an implementation of developing learning. In elementary school, it is useful to divide most children into groups based on the basic channel of perception. This allows a greater training effect. Although, the bone of contention is the training based on the type of child's temperament. This type is considered to be impractical in a traditional lesson system. This division is more suitable for extra-curricular activities such as the preparation of the play or concert. It is possible to apply a gender perspective at any stage of the lesson when working with any language material. Modern research shows there are quite large differences in the behavior and training of boys and girls due to a number of factors – biological, physiological, neuropsychological, social, psychological and pedagogical. Use of Games in the educational process Language learning is hard work. One must make an effort to understand, to repeat accurately, to manipulate, and to use the whole range of the target language in the conversation or written composition. Effort is required at every step and must be maintained for a long period of time. Games help and encourage many learners to keep their motivation and interest. Games also help

the teacher to create contexts in which language is useful and meaningful. The contribution of drilling lies in the concentration on a language form and its frequent use during a limited period of time. Many games provide this repeated use of a language form. If it is accepted that games can provide intense and meaningful practice of language, then they must be regarded as central to teacher's repertoire. Games can be found to give practice in all the skills (reading, writing, listening and speaking), in all the stages of the teaching/learning, sequence (presentation, repetition, recombination and free use of language) and for many types of communication functions (e.g. encouraging, criticizing, agreeing; explaining). Class and individual work, work in groups and in pairs Of the four types of grouping, pair and group work are very important if each learner is to have sufficient oral practice in the use of the language. In class work it is easy to demonstrate that learners say only one or two sentences in a lesson. The greatest "mistake" (if oral ability is an aim) is for the learner not to speak at all! The method of project work is worth mentioning too: it gives every student a good chance to show their creative individuality and develops their team spirit at the same time. Pair work is easy and fast to organize. It provides opportunities for intensive listening and speaking practice. Pair work is better than group work if there are discipline problems. Indeed, for all these reasons I often prefer to organize games in pair or general class work, rather than in group work.

5. Results Learners should be motivated by a desire to succeed, to explore, to develop and to improve, not by a fear of failure. We learn by doing. Young learners feel the need for a demonstration when they are learning any language skill. This is because they want to know how they can best do it, when and where it is appropriate to make use of their skill. Most learners prefer a concrete definition of their learning task . Conventional methods, techniques paved the way for the unified requirements for foreign language learning:

a child should master the language consciously;

training should not become an imitative process;

children should master the language as a medium of communication.

The main functions of the foreign language as a subject of the school curriculum are to develop willingness to use a foreign language as a means of communication, to familiarize with other national culture. To Sum up, this study is of relevance since it sheds light on a number of issues in the current theories. The implementation of these objectives requires teachers should know the psychological characteristics of primary schoolchildren to organize the educational process at this stage of training. Today nobody is to be convinced that early language training contributes not only more durable and practical knowledge, but also carries a great intellectual, educational potential. According to long-term observations early teaching of foreign languages:

- stimulates the language and overall development of children and, as a consequence, increases the value of comprehensive early childhood education and elementary education as the foundation of general education;
- attaches children to other cultures, thereby forming a universal consciousness;
- creates a favorable basis for mastering a foreign language, as well as for further language learning at later stages, as it prevents the formation of the psychological barriers that arise at the beginning of learning a foreign language at the age of 10-11 years old;
- improving general educational skills (e.g. ability to work with the book) by expanding their scope in the process of mastering a foreign language.

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